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Arctic Ocean Observation System

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Technologies and collaboration for sustained Arctic Ocean Observing Systems (A00S)

D4: User needs of in situ ocean observations in the Arctic

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Executive summary

The AOOS project is a planning and collaboration project under the Arktis 2030 programme, with the goal to strengthening the Norwegian role in development of ocean observations in the Arctic. This report, deliverable D4, is a contribution to the goal of the AOOS project, which is to develop a plan for implementation of an Arctic Ocean Observing System which will serve different scientific disciplines, public services and facilitate for innovation. The report describes the need for improvement, continuation and expansion of existing observing systems supporting different target groups.

The need for improvement and continuation of existing observing systems as well as to develop new observing systems is described for the different target groups for ocean data: **Climate research and services** need data for improving or establishing long time series of Essential Climate Variables for the ocean. **Marine monitoring and forecasting services** for weather, ocean and sea ice and marine ecosystems need near realtime data that feed into the forecasting models through data assimilation. **Environmental assessments** including pollution and other human impacts need systematic data to estimate changes in key environmental indicators over time. Monitoring systems for **Natural and man-made** hazards in marine environments have requirements for real-time data as well as statistical data for risk assessment. Man-made hazards are often connected to oil spills and other pollution from ships, offshore oil and gas activities, and other negative impacts of human activities on the environment.

Coverage and sampling of data in space and time is a critical factor because large areas of the Arctic Ocean have no data. Many areas have poor or sporadic data collection, while a few areas have moderate or good data coverage. There are numerous methods to measure in situ physical and biological variables using both automated instruments and lab analysis of water samples. For many biological and biogeochemical variables analysis of water samples is necessary, because these variables cannot be retrieved automatically in the same way as many physical measurements (e.g. temperature and salinity on moorings). This requires human effort and can be time consuming, implying that data cannot be delivered in near real time. **Data delivery chains** from the observing platforms to users need to satisfy requirements from different target groups. Marine forecasting needs near realtime delivery of data while climate services can use data delivered in delayed mode.

The user needs for data are constrained by the **observing platforms, instruments and sensors** that can produce the data (e.g., mooring systems, floats, drifters, seafloor installations, ice-based platforms, and ship based data from water samples). The report has therefore elaborated on the various observing methods that are applicable in the Arctic, and particularly in the ice-covered areas. New and promising observing methods for under ice environments are evolving based on AUVs/ROVs and use of subsea cables. A **vision for an integrated observing system** is to have a sustained network of autonomous moorings with multidisciplinary sensors observing the full water column. This network should be connected to subsea cables which can transfer data to land. The network will provide an acoustic positioning system which will enable navigation and positioning of AUVs, Argo floats and gliders while they move underwater in the central Arctic (hiaaos.eu).

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1. Introduction

A major goal of the AOOS project is to develop an implementation plan for an integrated ocean observing system for the Arctic based on international collaboration where Norwegian institutions have a central role. The general requirements for Arctic Ocean observing systems and background strategies for such systems were described in deliverable D1. Existing observing systems and the role of industry to develop the systems further were described in deliverable D2. In this report, D4, the requirements and recommendations for observations from different target groups are described. The requirements will be used as input to the specification and cost estimation of the ocean observing components, to be presented in deliverable D5.

The need for improvement and continuation of existing observing systems as well as to develop new observing systems is described for the different target groups for ocean data:

- Climate research and services need data for improving or establishing long time series of Essential Climate Variables for the ocean.
- Marine monitoring and forecasting services for weather, ocean and sea ice and marine ecosystems need near realtime data that feed into the forecasting models
- Environmental assessments including pollution and other human impacts need systematic data to estimate changes in key environmental indicators over time
- Natural and man-made hazards in marine environments have requirements for real-time monitoring and statistical data for risk assessment. Man-made hazards are oil spills and other pollution from ships, offshore oil and gas activities, deep sea mining, and pollution from land.
- Data delivery chains from the observing platforms to users need to satisfy requirements from different target groups. Marine forecasting needs near realtime delivery of data while climate services can use data delivered in delayed mode as long as they fulfill the quality requirements for climate data
- The user needs for data are constrained by the observing platforms, instruments and sensors that can produce the data (e.g., mooring systems, floats, drifters, seafloor installations, ship based data from water samples)

The high-level requirements for ocean observations in the coming years are outlined in the GOOS 2030 Strategy (Fig. 1.1). A central element of this strategy is the UN Decade of Ocean Science (2021-2030), which is a global endeavor to create a significant collaborative momentum for ocean-related sustainable development and science. Ocean observing is essential for a better understanding of how society and all life on earth is affected by climate change. The information gathered is invaluable to policymakers and individual nations, guiding them to make change at a global, regional and local level.

Our ocean, seas and coastal regions are critical to life on Earth, and a rapidly expanding 'blue economy' estimated to be worth \$3–6 trillion per year. The cumulative impacts of climate change, development, pollution and overfishing are placing considerable stress on our marine environment. We now know that the trajectory of change and damage threatens the future of our planet and all those that live on it. (From GOOS 2030 Strategy).

The Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) has defined a set of [Essential Ocean Variables](#) (EOV) representing global standards for the data to be collected to support different user groups. The EOVs are important to measure because they are the bases for ocean science, ocean monitoring and forecasting services, ecosystem management, natural hazard warning and other applications. The EOVs represent standards that respond to the requirements from different application areas and user groups. The EOVs specify which variables to observe, but not how, where and when the variables should be observed. Different observing technologies are used as new platforms and instruments becomes available. The standards provided by the EOVs ensure that consistent data sets are collected across observing methods.

Ocean information will be essential to supporting evidence-based decisions on the pathway to sustainable development.

Figure 1.1. Cover page and citation from the GOOS 2030 Strategy

The EOVs are divided into physics, biogeochemistry, and biosphere (biology and chemistry). An EOV can be subdivided into EOV products, which are measurable properties of an EOV. For example, “sea ice” is an EOV, while measurable products are “sea ice concentration”, “sea ice thickness” and others. Temperature is divided into “Sea-Surface temperature” and “Interior temperature”, where the former is observed by satellites and the latter is observed by various in situ instruments. The EOV products can be revised in response to new observing methods and new requirements from scientists and stakeholders.

In the polar seas there are large gaps in the observing systems because the sea ice cover makes it more difficult and expensive to install and operate in situ systems in these areas compared to the ice-free areas. Satellite observations play an essential role in observing the surface EOVs, in particular sea ice, surface temperature, surface height, currents, and other surface properties. However, most of the EOVs can only be obtained by in situ measurements covering the full water column from surface to bottom. Furthermore, the surface EOVs derived from satellite data need to have specific in situ observations to validate the satellite products.

The requirements for ocean observations to support research and applications in the Polar regions are described in several publications such as in Lee et al. (2019), Smith et al. (2019) and in reports from the [INTAROS project](#) (Sandven et al., 2022). Many papers on observational research in the Arctic have been published in *Oceanography* [Special Issue on “The New Arctic Ocean”](#) (Weingartner et al., 2022). In ice-free waters there are many autonomous platforms and sensors under development that can provide ocean data, while fewer systems that can be used in areas covered by ice. In the AOOS project it is therefore a goal to prepare a plan for implementation of ocean observing systems which include the ice-covered Arctic Ocean.

In this report the needs for in situ data from the Arctic Ocean in different target groups are described. The groups are: climate and climate services (section 2), marine forecasting services (section 3), environmental assessments, including pollution (section 4), and natural and man-made ocean hazards, impacts and mitigation (section 5). The requirements for observing platforms, instruments and methods to retrieve physical, biological, biochemical and pollution data are described in section 6, data delivery chains are described in section 7 and concluding remarks are presented in section 8. The results in this report will feed into the specification and cost estimation of implementing different components of an Arctic Ocean Observing System, to be presented in the subsequent D5 and D6 reports.

2. Climate and climate services

The [Global Climate Observing System program](#) (GCOS), a WMO program, collects and documents the data needs for monitoring the climate system, assessing the impacts of climate variability and understanding how it is changing. Global climate monitoring needs to cover the entire Earth system from the atmosphere to the oceans, from the cryosphere to the biosphere, and encompass the water, energy and carbon cycles. The 2022 [GCOS Implementation Plan](#) (GCOS-244) provides a set of high priority actions which will improve global observations of the climate system.

While satellite data plays an increasingly important role to provide some Essential Climate Variables (ECV) data, the *in situ* data have severe gaps in many regions, in particular in the polar regions and deep oceans. The situation has not improved much since the previous assessment report in 2015 ([GCOS-195](#)). The GCOS ECV Requirement report 2022 ([GCOS-245](#)) gives detailed specification of requirements for each of ECV.

The ocean ECVs, which are a sub-group of all ECVs (Fig. 2.1), are presented in Table 1 with corresponding ECV products. It is noted that some new ECV products have been specified between 2016 and 2022.

GCOS has collected specific requirements for ECV products from its expert panel and a wider community (see GCOS-244 Appendix 3). The requirements are specified for spatial resolution, temporal resolution (or frequency) measurement uncertainty, stability and timeliness.

Ocean		
ECV	ECV Product 2016	ECV Product 2022
Sea-Surface temperature	Sea-Surface temperature	Sea-Surface temperature
Subsurface Temperature	Interior Temperature	Interior Temperature
Sea-Surface Salinity	Sea-Surface Salinity	Sea-Surface Salinity
Subsurface Salinity	Interior Salinity	Interior Salinity
Surface Currents	Surface Geostrophic Current	Surface Geostrophic Current Ekman Currents
Subsurface Currents	Interior Currents	Vertical Mixing
Sea Level	Regional Sea Level	Regional Mean Sea Level
	Global Mean Sea Level	Global Mean Sea Level
Sea State	Wave Height	Wave Height
Surface Stress	Surface Stress	Surface Stress
Ocean Surface Heat Flux	Radiative Heat Flux	Radiative Heat Flux
	Sensible Heat Flux	Sensible Heat Flux
	Latent Heat Flux	Latent Heat Flux
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Concentration	Sea Ice Concentration
	Sea Ice Thickness	Sea Ice Thickness
	Sea Ice Drift	Sea Ice Drift
	Sea Ice Extent/Edge	Sea Ice Age
		Sea Ice Surface Temperature (IST)
		Sea ice Surface Albedo
		Snow Depth on Sea Ice
Oxygen	Interior Ocean Oxygen Concentration	Dissolved Oxygen Concentration
Nutrients	Interior Ocean Concentrations of Silicate, Phosphate, nitrate	Silicate
		Phosphate
		Nitrate
Ocean Inorganic Carbon	Interior Ocean Carbon Storage. (At least 2 of DIC, TA or pH)	Total Alkalinity (TA)
		Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC)
		pCO ₂
Transient Tracers	Interior Ocean CFC-11, CFC-12, SF ₆ , ¹⁴ C, tritium, ³ He, ³⁹ Ar	¹⁴ C
		SF ₆
		CFC-11
		CFC-12
Ocean nitrous oxide N ₂ O	Interior Ocean Nitrous Oxide N ₂ O	Interior Ocean Nitrous Oxide N ₂ O
	N ₂ O Air-Sea Flux	N ₂ O Air-Sea Flux
Ocean Colour	Water Leaving Radiance	Water Leaving Radiance
	Chlorophyll-a concentration	Chlorophyll-a concentration
Plankton	Zooplankton	Zooplankton Diversity
		Zooplankton Biomass
	Phytoplankton	Phytoplankton Diversity
		Phytoplankton Biomass
Marine Habitat Properties	Coral Reefs, mangrove forests, seagrass beds, Macroalgal Communities	Mangrove Cover and Composition
		Seagrass Cover (areal extent)
		Macroalgal Canopy Cover and Composition
		Hard coral cover and composition

Physics

Biogeochemistry

Biology

Table 1. List of ocean ECVs and ECV products, updated from 2016 to 2022 (from GCOS-244)

2.1 Areas – variables – sampling

For climate monitoring, research, and services, physical and biogeochemical ECV data are needed across the whole Arctic Ocean and the sub-Arctic seas (Fig. 2.2). The main ECVs are temperature, salinity, sea ice concentration and thickness, currents, sea level, ocean color, oxygen and several others. To better understand the coupled processes of the climate system, atmosphere ECV are also needed, e.g., air temperature, precipitation, wind, air pressure, and solar radiation. Priorities have been to collect data over several decades in the Norwegian Coastal waters, the Nordic Seas, the Barents Sea, and in the main straits between the North Atlantic, the Nordic Seas, the Barents Sea, and the Arctic Ocean.

Climate services rely on a well-structured ocean observation network with optimized temporal sampling (measurement frequency) and spatial coverage (geographic distribution) to deliver accurate, reliable, and actionable climate information. The specific requirements depend on the observed parameter, its application, and the region (e.g., Barents Sea vs. Central Arctic Ocean, surface ocean vs. deep ocean). In general, long-term observations - particularly in key regions (e.g., Central Arctic Ocean and Arctic Gateways) - are essential for tracking climate change and its impacts over time (Fig. 2.2).

Figure 2.2. (a) Main ocean currents in the Arctic Ocean, including Atlantic Water (red), Pacific Water (pink/blue), and surface water (blue) [Credit: Fig. 3 of Carmack et al., 2015; © American Meteorological Society.

These observations should be extended into the ice-covered deep Arctic Ocean where much less data have been collected. The need for more ocean data is pressing because of the extreme climate change in this region with severe impact on ecosystems, fisheries, offshore industry, shipping, and management of the marine and coastal environment.

2.2 Target groups

Climate monitoring centers play a crucial role in collecting data and delivering reliable information on the Arctic’s past, present, and future climate. In Norway the [Norwegian Climate Service Centre](#) (NCCS) is a collaboration between the Norwegian Meteorological Institute, the Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate, Norwegian Research Centre, the Norwegian Mapping Authority, and the Bjerknes Center for Climate Research (BCCR). NCCS compiles and disseminates climate and hydrological data, facilitating climate adaptation efforts and advancing research on the effects of climate change on nature and society (Fig. 2.3). Universities and research institutes require observations from all regions shown in Fig. 2.2 to quantify key physical processes such as ocean circulation, water mass changes, heat and freshwater fluxes, ocean-atmosphere interactions, and ocean-sea ice dynamics. For example, BCCR is the largest climate research center in the Nordic countries and a leading institution in Europe. BCCR has an international reputation for expertise in climate science, modeling, and scenario development for future climate change. Researchers also rely on observational data to validate climate models and analyze long-term climate trends.

a

b

Figure 2.3 (a) Cover page of report from the Norwegian Centre for Climate Service on sea level rise in Norway (b) Tide gauge observations (black markers) and observation-based extrapolations (blue) for three cities in Norway. Medium confidence Relative Sea Level change (RSL) projections showing the median (red line) and likely ranges (red shaded) for SSP3-7.0. Baseline period is 1995-2014. (Simpson et al., 2024).

In Norway, the primary institutions involved in climate modeling have established the Infrastructure for Norwegian Earth System Modelling (INES) (<https://www.ines.noresm.org/>). Its core mission is to provide an advanced Earth system modeling infrastructure to support climate mitigation and adaptation strategies. INES produces and disseminates climate and hydrological data to aid climate change adaptation and assess the impacts of climate change on ecosystems and society. [Climate](#)

[Futures](#) is a Centre for Research-based Innovation funded by the Research Council of Norway from 2020. Its goal is to generate long-term cooperation between companies, public organizations and research groups across sectors and disciplines for developing climate prediction for handling climate risk.

Climate research centers rely on observational data to produce climate reanalyses—comprehensive reconstructions of the climate system across time and space. For example, the [ECMWF](#) has long been committed to generating global atmospheric and ocean reanalyses, such as [ERA5](#) and [ORAS5](#). At the regional level, [TOPAZ](#), a coupled ocean–sea ice data assimilation system developed at NERSC, provides reanalyses for the North Atlantic Ocean and the Arctic. These climate reanalyses are vital for studying climate variability, understanding key climate processes, and initializing climate predictions. A comparison between climate model outputs, reanalysis data and cruise data is shown in Fig 2.4. The data were collected in the US-Norwegian CAATEX project (Worcester et al., 2020) in the Central Arctic Ocean (Langehaug et al., 2023).

a

b

Figure 2.4. (a) Different models from Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) are compared with cruise data in the Eurasian part of the CAATEX section. They use the 300-700m layer (shown in b) to capture the mid-layer as representation Atlantic Water in the Arctic Ocean (Langehaug et al., 2023).

The results of the climate research are used in many (1) [assessment reports for IPCC](#), Arctic Council (through AMAP, PAME, and other working groups), Norwegian and international agencies, industries and non-governmental organisations (NGOs), (2) policy and strategy documents dealing with climate change issues, and (3) climate adaptation and mitigation plans for municipalities in Norway. The assessment reports provide science-based knowledge about climate and environmental changes and give policy-relevant recommendations to support informed decision-making by governments and regional authorities.

Climate prediction centers rely on in-situ data to enhance Arctic climate forecasts. For example, the ECMWF provides atmospheric and oceanic condition forecasts up to seven months in advance. These forecasts are generated monthly using a 51-member ensemble with a horizontal resolution of approximately 36 km. The [Bjerknes Climate Prediction Unit](#) (Bjerknes CPU) is working on improving climate predictions across sub-seasonal, seasonal, and decadal timescales, bridging the gap between weather forecasting and long-term climate change projections. The [Norwegian Climate Prediction Model](#) (NorCPM) produces a new seasonal forecast once every month. Examples of such forecasts are shown in Fig. 2.5.

Figure 2.5 Forecasts of temperature (left) and precipitation (right) for June 2025 presented as probability that June 2025 will be warmer/wetter than normal relative to the 1993 – 2016 climatology (<https://bcpu.w.uib.no/seasonal-forecast/>).

The [Copernicus Climate Change Service](#) (C3S) publishes seasonal forecasts on a regular basis, drawing from several leading climate centers around the world, including the [WMO Lead Centre for Annual-to-Decadal Climate Prediction](#). The Centre, hosted by UK Met Office, produces and disseminates annual forecasts of the climate for the next 1-10 years. The C3S in collaboration with WMO produced the [2024 European State of the Climate report](#) (ESOTC), describing key events and their impact, trends in climate indicators and climate policies and actions. The report also addresses the climate conditions across the Arctic for sea ice extent and thickness, surface temperature and ocean colour for the ice-free areas.

3. Marine forecasting services

Marine forecasting services are based on a combination of numerical circulation models, associated forcing data from numerical weather prediction, hydrology data and observations. These elements are used in data assimilation, which is necessary to obtain the best estimate of the initial state of the ocean, which in turn leads to higher quality in the forecasts. There are many different methods for data assimilation, which are all based on some form of weighting between observation and model data using error statistics, possibly constrained by model physics or predetermined balancing conditions between control variables.

Ocean forecasting systems can vary widely with regards to geographical extent and level of detail. In general, as a result of increased need for computing resources, the higher the resolution, the smaller the geographical extent. Hence operational forecasting systems are designed according to a nested configuration, with global models providing lateral boundary conditions to regional models, which in turn provide lateral boundary conditions to national coastal ocean forecasting systems, e.g. the "Norkyst" system for the coast of mainland Norway (Fig. 3.1b).

Figure 3.1 (a) Map of the regional systems providing the Copernicus Marine Services, with responsible institutions for the in situ Thematic Assembly Centres in each region. (b) Map of sea surface temperature from the TOPAZ model (colour scale from light yellow to dark red) where the green box shows the Norkyst system and the blue box the Barents system.

In Europe it is the [Copernicus Marine Service](#) that provides ocean forecasts on global and regional scales, with the production of the latter delegated to Monitoring and Forecasting Centers (MFC), as

shown in Fig. 3.1a. The Arctic MFC is based in Norway and coordinated by NERSC, with IMR and MET Norway as partners. The international scientific collaboration on ocean forecasting is coordinated by various organisations, of which [Ocean Predict](#) with its associated task teams, is one of the most relevant.

The Norwegian service providers needing observations are primarily MET Norway, NERSC, IMR, and NPI. MET Norway has the operational high performance computing infrastructure for ocean forecasting, co-producing both the Copernicus Marine system for the Arctic and the national forecasting models. All these four institutions also produce model data that is not time critical, either as hindcasts or reanalyses, which then require observations for either model verification or data assimilation.

3.1 Areas – variables – sampling

Marine forecasting services for the Arctic are provided through the [Arctic MFC](#) the coupled ocean-sea ice modeling system TOPAZ, which produces operational forecasts at 5-6 km resolution with a forecast length of 10 days. The area of the service includes the whole Arctic Ocean and the Nordic Seas north of 60N (Fig. 3.1a). National systems operated by MET Norway are nested into TOPAZ. The two main forecasting systems are "Norkyst", which is co-developed with IMR, and "Barents". Norkyst covers the coast of mainland Norway while Barents covers the Barents Sea and the regions around Svalbard. Example of sea ice and ocean temperature forecasting is illustrated in Fig. 3.2. A brief description of the models is provided at <https://ocean.met.no/models>.

Figure 3.2. The Barents Sea coupled ocean and sea ice ensemble prediction model, showing ocean temperature in colours and sea ice concentration in grey-white (<https://ocean.met.no/models#barents>).

The ocean model components use sea surface temperature (SST) and sea level anomalies (SLA) from satellites, and vertical profiles of salinity and temperature from in situ instruments. Increased focus on ocean biogeochemistry means that ocean colour observations from satellite, and biogeochemical (BGC) parameters from in situ platforms, will become increasingly relevant. Sea ice models require remote sensing data from Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) or Passive Microwave instruments (PMW), and in general cannot take directly advantage of in situ observations.

For marine forecasting services, the necessary spatial resolution varies depending on product, but in general there is no upper limit on what resolution that can be of potential use for verification and data assimilation purposes. Typical resolution today for remote sensing data is of order 1-10km, which matches assimilative systems currently in use, but operational forecasting systems with a resolution of order 100m are coming online, and flexible assimilation schemes/AI algorithms will be able to make use of very high-resolution observations, in particular in post processing steps. For in situ data there is a serious lack of hydrographic measurements below the surface layer, and the greatest need is more profiles of salinity and temperature, especially in dynamically active regions such as in the NCC or on the Arctic Ocean frontal zones. Temporal sampling should resolve tidal and inertial periods mesoscale eddies to capture the "weather of the ocean", implying that hourly sampling is adequate. Examples of wave forecasting and current forecasting are shown in Fig. 3.3.

Figure 3.3. (a) The pan-Arctic wave model WAM3 showing significant wave height in the open ocean areas of the Arctic, provided through the Copernicus Arctic MFC (<https://ocean.met.no/waves#wavewatch>); (b) Surface current off the coast of Northern Norway from an operational ocean model which assimilates current data from the HF radar network along the coast. The red circle indicates where data from the Fruholmen radar (red star) is used (Röhrs et al., 2021).

3.2 Target groups

Users of marine forecasts are a diverse group, but can in general be divided into three categories: Users that need decision support for emergencies, e.g. search-and-rescue, harmful algal blooms, oil

spills, ship drift, and so on; users that need decision support for safe operations, such as fishing vessels, navigators, operators of offshore installations,; and users that need historical information about the physical state of the ocean for research or management purposes.

For the first two groups, access to real-time information is critical, which is why marine forecasting service providers place great emphasis on data assimilation and access to near-real time (NRT) observations with basic quality control flags. For the third group, marine forecast service providers will optimally deliver high quality model reanalysis data. To produce such reanalyses, the service providers focus on collecting as much observations as possible (both NRT and delayed mode) and prefer to have more advanced quality control of the information if available, but the main priority is to have as much observational data as possible.

Copernicus Marine Service users span a wide range of sectors, including marine policy, blue growth industries, scientific research, and public awareness. Key groups include marine policy implementers, those involved in blue economy activities, scientists, decision-makers, and the general public. The service is designed to support these diverse user groups by providing free and open access to high-quality ocean data and information. Copernicus Marine Services are user-driven, as shown in Fig. 3.4.

Figure 3.4 Illustration of the user feedback process as described in [2024 User Feedback Report](#).

In Norway, the target groups for marine forecasting services are primarily fisheries, offshore oil and gas industry, aquaculture, ship traffic and tourism. The governmental agencies responsible for maritime activities are [Norwegian Coastal Administration](#), [Norwegian Maritime Authority](#) and [Directorate of Fisheries](#). Regarding search and rescue, the [Joint Rescue and Coordination Center](#), (JRCC), has the overall responsibility with a wide range of resources from several agencies to its disposal. More information about these agencies and safety at sea is provided in section 4 and 5.

4. Ecosystems, environment and pollution

Ecological processes in the ocean are strongly influenced by physical parameters. In the Arctic Ocean sea ice plays a special role since it serves as a habitat for a diverse range of organisms, from unicellular protists to macrofauna and fish. However, ice also limits light penetration into the water column, and the freeze-melt cycle affects stratification and mixing processes, regulating the replenishment of essential nutrients in the euphotic zone. This leads to pronounced seasonality in the availability of photosynthetically fixed carbon in the Arctic marine environment. Furthermore, the influx of water from boreal regions introduces both boreal species and pollutants into the Arctic, while the Arctic Ocean itself encompasses a wide range of habitats from shallow shelf seas to deep sea basins as illustrated in Fig. 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Arctic pelagic ecosystem and its connection to the sympagic (ice-associated) and benthic ecosystem. Ice algae and phytoplankton are consumed by zooplankton, including benthic larvae. The presence of lipid rich zooplankton sustains the resident predator community and attracts migratory predators (fish, sea birds, whales) to assemble along the marginal ice zone during summer. Inflow of water masses from the Atlantic and Pacific leads to advection of boreal species. Organic material consisting of non-consumed algae and faecal pellets are either recycled and remineralized within the water column, or sink to the sea floor where the material is recycled and remineralized by benthic communities. Vertical migration of zooplankton and fish facilitate the carbon export to deeper waters. (Daase et al 2021).

Climate-driven sea ice decline, warming, and changing oceanographic patterns can profoundly impact Arctic ecosystems by altering community composition, food web dynamics (Fig. 4.2), and energy flow between sympagic (ice-associated), pelagic, and benthic systems. Northward expansion of boreal species has been observed, but their ability to establish stable populations or compete with native Arctic species remains unclear. Additionally, sea ice loss increases open water areas and enhances light penetration, potentially affecting primary production—yet the dynamics of these changes are poorly understood.

Despite growing research, significant gaps remain in our understanding of how Arctic biota respond to environmental changes. For instance, the biodiversity of sea ice communities is still largely unknown. While some species demonstrate plasticity in feeding and life cycles, habitat loss poses a threat to ice-dependent organisms, with largely unknown repercussions for energy transfer and ecosystem functioning (Bluhm et al. 2018, Hop et al 2021).

The rapid transformation of Arctic ecosystems underscores the need for standardized sampling and long-term monitoring of environmental parameters. Advancing innovative technologies will be crucial for addressing current knowledge gaps and improving predictions of Arctic marine ecosystem responses to ongoing climate change.

Figure 4.2 Schematic of the connection between sea ice decline and food web interactions of ice associated biota in the recent past (left) and near future (right) in the Arctic. Changes in size of organisms between scenarios functions as an indicator of the expected increase or decrease in populations sizes and/or abundances.

4.1 Areas – variables – sampling

There is currently no systematic monitoring of biology and environment in the Central Arctic Ocean, however, the [Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Program](#) (CBMP) under CAFF (Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna) has a key role to report on the status. CBMP is a network professionals and organisations observing and detecting changes in the major Arctic marine, freshwater, terrestrial and coastal ecosystems. CBMP created the marine biodiversity monitoring plan in 2011, the first [Arctic Marine Biodiversity Report in 2017](#) (CAFF, 2017) and follow-up reports. The report defines eight Arctic Marine Areas and gives a status of monitoring activities of different species in each of them (Fig. 4.3).

Figure 4.3: Status of monitoring activities for each Focal Ecosystem Component (i.e., selected species groups) across each Arctic Marine Area. Adapted from the CAFF 2017 report: [State of the Arctic Marine Biodiversity Report \(SAMBR\)](#)

The report shows that most of the Arctic areas have “poor”, “sporadic” or “none” monitoring activities. The most extensive ecosystem monitoring program exists in the Barents Sea, which is included in the “Atlantic-Arctic” area (Fig. 4.3). The program covers all ecosystem components in ice-free areas and is conducted by IMR from Norway and [PINRO](#) from Russia. This program has been a collaboration between Russia and Norway since 1958 and is still ongoing because management of the fisheries is important for both countries. A 50 year anniversary book on his collaboration was published in 2011 (Jacobsen and Ozhigin, 2011, Fig. 4.4 left).

In recent years several major research programs have been conducted in the Barents Sea and the Central Arctic Ocean, where large amount of physical, biological and biogeochemical data were collected. The [Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate expedition \(MOSAiC\)](#) was a one-year-long expedition into the Central Arctic lasting for a year with more than 600 people from 20 countries. Results from these large projects have produced significant new insight into the Arctic environment and will produce more knowledge in the coming years. The [Nansen Legacy project](#) was a Norwegian collaboration between 10 institutions and 280 people from 2018 to 2024. The goal is to provide integrated scientific knowledge on the rapidly changing marine climate and ecosystem to facilitate a sustainable management of the northern Barents Sea and adjacent Arctic Basin through the 21st century.

Figure 4.4 Left: Cover page of a book about the Barents Sea giving extensive insight into 50 years of research (Jacobsen and Ozhigin, 2011). Centre: Cover page of State of the Arctic Marine Biodiversity report (CAFF 2017). Right: Map of the MOSAiC Drift Expedition (Fong et al. 2024).

For Svalbard and surrounding waters “[Miljøovervåking Svalbard og Jan Mayen](#)” is an environmental monitoring program for a number of indicators, including pollutants in selected marine vertebrates, populations size and/or biomass of marine mammals, seabirds, key fish species, as well as zooplankton in Kongsfjorden and the Barents Sea. In addition, environmental parameters are currently measured on research cruises or with moored instruments in connection with research projects (e.g. Isfjorden monitoring by UNIS, Kongfjorden and Rijpfjorden moorings by UiT). The Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observation System ([SIOS](#)) produces the annual [SESS report](#) about the state of the environment in the Svalbard region based on the international research activities organized under SIOS. The marine activities in SIOS for 2024 has been summarized by Bensi et al., (2025).

In the Fram Strait, north-east of Svalbard, and in the Nansen and Amundsen Basin, have moorings to collect oceanographic and biological data. These moorings are part of the [Atlantic-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatory](#) (A-DBO), a network to coordinate all environmental observations in the Atlantic Sector of the Arctic in order to facilitate both long-term and project-based sampling, data sharing and harmonize sampling and analysis procedures. Environmental data includes a wide range biological and biogeochemical variables on different tropic levels. A description of instruments and methods for sampling the different variables is given in section 6.

Sampling and coverage

The spatial sampling and coverage of environmental data is in general lacking in ice-covered areas (Fig. 4.3) so our knowledge of environmental processes in these areas is very poor. The goal of developing and operating environmental observing systems in the Arctic is to improve our

understanding of the influence of boreal influx into the Arctic as well as processes in the Arctic itself and the outflow area. We also need a better observational basis on how changes in the sea-ice cover, upper-ocean mixed layer and vertical fluxes of nutrients influence the base of the food chain; primary production. Thus, monitoring should cover a wide geographical range, including the inflow area (eastern Fram Strait, shelf slope north of Svalbard), the central Arctic Ocean (Nansen and Amundsen Basin), and the outflow shelf and slope (western Fram Strait). Vertical resolution: environmental parameters should be monitored throughout the water column, but the capacity to observe large volumes of the ocean is limited.

Temporal resolution and seasonal coverage of the biological and biogeochemical data are critical for understanding the marine environment. Ecosystem processes in the Arctic are highly affected by the seasonality in incoming solar radiation and ice cover. Traditionally, ecological studies have focused on summer months (when the Arctic is most easily accessible); less data is available from other seasons, particularly from the central Arctic and from polar night/winter (Berge et al. 2020).

Regarding pollution in the Arctic AMAP has conducted numerous studies and published [a series of reports](#) since its establishment in 1991. The reports have assessed the presence and effects of Persistent Organic Pollutants (POP), heavy metals, radioactivity, acidification, petroleum hydrocarbons, stratospheric ozone, short-lived climate forcers (black carbon, methane), plastic pollution (Fig. 4.5) and how climate change can alter the pathways and effects of the contaminants.

Figure 4.5. Impacts of litter and microplastics on Arctic biota (AMAP, 2025)

The most recent report is about the effects of plastic pollution on the environment. It shows that plastic pollution is widely spread in the Arctic with a range of negative impacts on animals and ecosystems (AMAP 2025). It is therefore urgent to take actions to reduce plastic litter, where legally binding regulations will be an important tool. Data on pollution is dependent on the collection of environmental data in general and how these data can be used to study effects. New technologies for sampling water and analyze the contents of plastics and other pollutants are in progress (section 6).

Warming and changes in sea ice will likely affect the timing of biological process, in particular onsets and duration of algae blooms, which has repercussions throughout the food web. It's therefore recommended to aim for seasonal coverage in monitoring. This will provide better understanding of the impact of changes in the physical environment on primary production, and the effects of changes in algae blooms on secondary producers, as well as the ability of boreal species to establish themselves further north.

Marine protected areas are of particular interest to monitor because it is necessary to document how well these areas are protected over time. In 2013, the Arctic Council identified “Areas of heightened ecological and cultural significance” covering an area of approximately 76 % of the Arctic marine area (Figure 4.6). However, in 2021 only about 5 % of the Arctic marine area was protected. It is a common goal for the various international conventions, councils and organisations involved in the Arctic to protect the marine environment and follow up the vision of clean, healthy and productive ocean as formulated by the UN Decade of Ocean Science 2021-2030.

Figure 4.6. Arctic Ecologically and Biologically Significant Areas (EBSAs) and Arctic Marine Areas of Heightened Ecological and Cultural Significance as identified in the [Arctic Marine Shipping Assessment \(AMSA\) IIC report](#).” (AMAP/CAFF/SDWG, 2013).

4.2 Target groups

In Norway the target groups for observation of marine ecosystems, environment and pollution include a wide range of institutions, from ministries and agencies to research institutions, fisheries and other ocean industries, educational institutions, municipalities and NGOs. The knowledge derived from the observations, are used to prepare assessments reports and strategy documents, which feed into policy and decision making. Institute of Marine Research, in collaboration with many other institutes, provides data and knowledge about the marine environment including the whole food chain from plankton to sea food. The Institute is the main advisory body for the [Directorate of Fisheries](#), which is the responsible authority for fisheries and aquaculture. The [Norwegian Environment Agency](#) is the regulatory authority and advisory body for environmental protection and pollution prevention of land, air and sea. The Agency collaborates with the [Coastal Administration](#) and Directorate of Fisheries in cases of acute pollution of the sea such as oil spoils or harmful algal blooms. Havtil is the [Norwegian Ocean Industry Authority](#) supervising companies on safety and environmental issues.

Internationally, the target groups include a number of intergovernmental organisations, councils and committees. The Arctic Council has several working groups dealing with the marine environment: [CAFF](#) (Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna) that focuses on conservation of Arctic biodiversity; [AMAP](#) (Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme) who monitor pollution, climate change as well as key climate indicators and their impact on Arctic ecosystems and residents. [PAME](#) (Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment) works with marine policy and sea-based activities in the Arctic and [ACAP](#) (Arctic Contaminants Action Program) works to prevent and reduce pollution and environmental risks in the Arctic. [EPPR](#) (Emergency prevention, Preparedness and Response) contributes to prevention, preparedness and response to environmental and other emergencies, accidents and search and rescue.

Target groups also include [International Council for Exploration of the Seas](#) (ICES), an intergovernmental organization with the mission “*To advance and share scientific understanding of marine ecosystems and the services they provide and to use this knowledge to generate state-of-the-art advice for meeting conservation, management, and sustainability goals*” (ICES, 2021). ICES has several committees, expert groups and working groups. One is the Working Group on Integrated Ecosystem Assessment (IEA) for the Central Arctic Ocean (Fig. 4.7). Preparing an IEA for this unexplored region is essential for providing scientific advice on issues such as the prospect for future fisheries and the sensitivity and vulnerability of the ecosystem to shipping.

The [Central Arctic Ocean Fisheries Agreement](#) (CAOFA) was signed in 2018 by 8 countries and the EU (Fig. 4.7b). The objective is to prevent unregulated High Seas Fisheries in the Central Arctic Ocean. Under this agreement the [Joint Program of Scientific Research and Monitoring Framework](#) (JPSRM) was signed in 2023 and has now an implementation plan, secure data sharing portal and a public website. Other target groups include the [Oslo Paris Convention](#) (OSPAR) and its Arctic Outcome Working Group, which is committed to take steps to protect the Arctic marine environment in the OSPAR area (Fig. 4.7a).

Figure 4.7 (a) OSPAR region I (Arctic waters) and ICES ecoregions shown by the numbers, and (b) boundary of the CAOFA region.

Other target groups are NGOs, where [WWF Global Arctic Programme](#), is one of the most prominent organisations working for nature conservation in the Arctic. The programme produces a number of reports, news articles and other information material about environmental and policy issues in the Arctic. A recent report describes the implications and opportunities of the [“High Seas Treaty”](#) in the Arctic (Molenaar, 2024). The Treaty has focus on conservation and sustainable use of marine ecosystems in areas beyond national jurisdiction (ANBJ) and is part of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea ([UNCLOS](#)).

Norway has ratified the BBNJ Agreement – “On duty for the Ocean” (04 June 2025).

“Today, I am proud and delighted to announce that Norway has ratified and will join as the 31st party to the BBNJ* Agreement. Protecting the world’s oceans requires collective effort from all countries. This is why Norway has been a driving force in landing this Agreement”, says Minister of Foreign Affairs Espen Barth Eide.

“This new international ocean agreement will help us reach the goal from the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework of protecting 30 percent of marine areas by 2030”, said Minister of Climate and Environment Andreas Bjelland Eriksen.

* [Agreement on Marine Biological Diversity of Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction](#) under UN, also called the “High Seas Treaty”

The European Union is a target group because of its integrated policy for the Arctic, where research plays a central role. In EU’s [updated Arctic policy](#) from 2021, the aim is to help preserve the Arctic as a region of peaceful cooperation, to slow the effects of climate change, and to support the sustainable development of Arctic regions to the benefit of Arctic communities, not least Indigenous Peoples, and future generations. EU has become a major funder of Arctic research programmes and projects, supplementing national and other programmes (https://www.eas.europa.eu/eas/eu-arctic-fundingprogrammes_en).

5. Natural and manmade hazards, impacts and mitigation

Observing systems are needed to detect and respond to natural hazards which can occur quickly and can have severe consequences for human lives and activities in ocean and coastal areas. These include earthquakes, tsunamis, coastal flooding, extreme sea ice events and icebergs, harmful algal blooms, marine avalanches, and marine heat wave events. Observations are also needed to detect manmade hazards and influences such as oil spills and other types of pollution caused by ship accidents, aquaculture plants, offshore wind farms or pollution from land. The observing systems need to provide data in near realtime and cover large areas. Satellite data and airborne observations play a key role to monitor ship traffic and detect hazardous events such as oil spill and harmful algal blooms. However, in situ data are needed to detect and determine other types of pollution, but the in situ systems have poor spatial coverage, implying that there are large areas without any data.

In addition to the rapid and unpredicted hazards, there are influences and threats developing over time such as consequences of climate change, oil and gas production, fisheries, ship traffic and other human activities.

Impact of fisheries, offshore industry and shipping in the Arctic

The oceans are impacted by industrial activities in different ways and the Arctic Ocean is no exception. In the ice-covered areas, human activities have been limited so far, but ship traffic is growing because the sea ice is diminishing and the potential for economic development is increasing. The main economic activities in the Arctic are connected to fisheries, oil and gas exploitation and tourism, all of them are generating ship traffic and have impact on the environment in different ways as illustrated in Fig. 5.1.

Figure 5.1. Environmental impact of human activities (Elshout et al., 2023).

The Arctic Council's PAME working group published the Arctic Marine Shipping Assessment report (AMSA, 2009), which provided a framework policy document for the Arctic states. In a follow-up report Arctic marine areas of heightened ecological and cultural significance were identified (AMSA/CAFF/SDWG, 2013). The recommendations from AMSA have been guidelines for development of sustainable Arctic shipping. From 2012 the Norwegian Coastal Administration has been monitoring ship traffic in real time using AIS data from satellites and coastal stations. The same

data has been collected and archived by PAME's [Arctic Ship Traffic Data project](#) for the Polar Code area (Fig. 5.2). AIS was introduced by the [International Maritime Organisation](#) (IMO) in 2002 to improve ship traffic safety and the environment, and to strengthen maritime traffic services. In AIS data are mandatory for ships above 300 tons or with more than 12 people. This means that ships are monitored in near realtime and information is presented at the website such as [Marine Vessel Traffic](#). The AIS data provides useful statistics on ship traffic within the Polar Code area, which is used in a number of environmental studies because the AIS data contain information about fuel consumption (air emission) and other impacts (Qi et al., 2024).

Underwater noise in the Arctic is generated from natural processes and marine life (e.g. weather and sea ice, earthquakes, marine mammals) as well as from human activities, especially ship traffic, seismic surveys and other industries. Noise from increasing ship traffic is recognized as an environmental issue that has impacts on Arctic species, ecosystems and ecosystem services. On this background PAME has produced the reports "[Underwater Noise Pollution from shipping in the Arctic](#)" (PAME, 2021) and [Underwater Noise in the Arctic](#), (PAME, 2025). These reports recommend that one of the next actions should be to build an acoustic monitoring network as basis for generating new knowledge and management practices regarding noise from ship traffic.

The [Polar Code](#) (International Code for Ships Operating in Polar Waters), which is part of the SOLAS and MARPOL conventions, defines mandatory requirements to vessels regarding ship safety and protection of the unique environment and eco-systems of the polar regions. The International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea ([SOLAS](#)), from 1974 is regarded as the most important of all international treaties concerning the safety of merchant ships.

Figure 5.2 Ship tracks of all ships in 2024 within the Polar Code area: (a) fishing vessels which are the largest category of vessels, representing 39% of all the ships in 2024, (b) general cargo vessels is the second largest category, representing 10 % of all the ships. ([PAME Arctic Shipping Status Report #1, 2025](#)).

The International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships ([MARPOL](#)) is the main international convention covering prevention of pollution of the marine environment by ships from operational or accidental causes.

Fishing vessels, which represent that largest group of ships, can impact the marine environment in different ways, e.g. by pollution from lost equipment or oil leakage, carbon emission from fuel burning, overfishing, bottom trawling, invasive species through ballast water and more. Studies on lost fishing gear have shown that this is an important source of global marine pollution, with negative impacts to wildlife, marine and coastal habitats, and food security (Richardson et al., 2022). Marine pollution in the Arctic is well documented in Svalbard, where [beach clean-up activities](#) have been organized by the Governor of Svalbard for many years. Tourist operators, local organisations and other volunteers are actively involved in the clean-up, which is crucial for the protection of the fragile Arctic environment and for raising awareness about marine pollution.

The Northern Sea Route is the most important shipping route in the Arctic because of the development of the Russian gas fields in Yamal, one of the largest natural gas production sites in the world (Fig. 5.3).

Figure 5.3. (a) Photo is the Yamal LNG production facilities in Sabetta (from <http://yamallng.ru/en/>); (b) Map of the traffic pattern of LNG tankers sailing to Sabetta in the Yamal peninsula (<http://www.astd.is>); (c) Photo of “Christophe de Margerie”, the first generation Arc7 ice class LNG tanker, built in 2016 with gross tonnage of 128806 tons. It completed its first voyage with through the Northern Sea Route to South Korea in August 2017. Photo from: <https://www.bairdmaritime.com/shipping/tankers/gas/christophe-de-margerie-breaks-nsr-transit-records>

Most of the gas is transported as liquified natural gas (LNG) by ships, including use of specialized ARC7 iceclass LNG carriers which can operate year-round in sea ice. The oil and gas sector is the largest emitter of climate gases and also the sector with significant risks for pollution from production and transport of oil and gas. The [Centre for High North Logistics](#) (CHNL) monitors and produces statistics of the ship traffic in the Northern Sea route. A total of 21.2 mill tons of LNG was exported from the Yamal plant in 287 voyages during 2024, an amount which increases year by year ([High North News, 29 April 2025](#)).

Tourism in the Arctic is a growing industry, especially expedition cruises which offer new and adventurous destinations to remote areas. These cruises have impact on the environment and challenges connected to safety, because there is lack of infrastructure to support or rescue people and vessels in case of accidents. Longyearbyen in Svalbard, which is a hub for the Arctic cruise expeditions, experience increased demand for infrastructure, port facilities and services for the vessels. The [Association of Arctic Expedition Operators](#) (AECO) is a member organization of vessel owners, tourist operators and others involved in cruise tourism in several Arctic regions (Fig. 5.4).

Figure 5.4. Upper map showing the areas where AECO members organize tourist expeditions in the Arctic. The photograph is of MS Roald Amundsen, the new tourist vessel owned by Hurtigruten Expedition. The state-of-the-art vessel features new and environmentally sustainable hybrid technology that will reduce fuel consumption and show the world that hybrid propulsion on large ships is possible.

The main goal of AECO is to develop sustainable cruise tourism in the Polar regions by ensuring that the cruise tourism is environmentally friendly, responsible, safe and follows rules and regulations. It means that the industry must balance between economic profit, environmental protection and the interest of local communities where the tourists visit. AECO is building competence in their member organization through development of [guidelines for the tourist guides and the tourists](#).

Shipping activities in Arctic waters involve several risk factors: navigation can be difficult, grounding can occur because bathymetry charts have poor quality in many regions, vessels can be damaged by sea ice or icebergs, and technical problems with vessels can be difficult to solve because assistance is not available. There have been numerous ship accidents in the Arctic and Antarctica over the years, where vessels have been trapped in ice, collided with ice or in some cases sunk because the hull was damaged (Fig. 5.5). Rescue operations are often difficult because resources are far away and it takes time to bring in personnel and equipment to assist the vessels.

Figure 5.5 (a) The cruise ship MS Explorer sank after striking an iceberg in the Antarctic Ocean on November 23rd 2007 <https://www.nbcnews.com/id/wbna21935099>. (b and c) The cruise ship MS Maxim Gorky hit sea ice near Svalbard and got damaged in the hull. The ship started to sink and all 950 passengers and crew member were evacuated on the ice. All were rescued by the Norwegian Coast Guard and the ship was repaired (Courtesy Natalia Marchenko, UNIS, Photos by Odd Mydland)

Environmental impact, as illustrated in Fig. 5.1, is to a large extent caused by ship traffic and offshore industry activities. To mitigate the risk factors the Polar Code has defined a set of standards for ship safety, which includes ship design, construction, equipment, operations, manning and training. Regarding environmental protection there are requirements for oil and lubricants, sewage and garbage treatment to avoid any discharges into the sea. Use of heavy fuel oil (HFO) is banned in the Arctic effective from 2024, as part of amendments to MARPOL.

Why safety is a challenge in the Arctic

- cold conditions and extreme weather conditions, leading to higher risk that people and equipment will not function
- remoteness and long distances imply that assistance in case of accidents will take much longer time
- limited infrastructure, implying that most human activities are more difficult and time consuming
- climate change is stronger, leading to more extreme weather events and consequently more severe natural hazards

The Arctic Council working group [EPPR](#) (Emergency Prevention, Preparedness and Response) is a forum for collaboration to advance risk mitigation and improve response capabilities in the Arctic. EPPR has expert groups working on

- Search and Rescue agreements
- Marine Environmental Response
- Radiation

The background for the radiation work is that ship traffic in the Arctic includes nuclear-powered vessels, ships transporting spent nuclear fuel and high-level radioactive waste, and the operation of a floating nuclear power plant. The expert groups produce publications, participates in exercises, develops tools and guidelines, and run projects.

Natural hazards

There are several natural hazards in the marine environment, such as extreme weather events, sea ice and icebergs, earthquakes and seabed slides (Fig. 5.6). The operational weather, sea ice and iceberg services use data from satellites, land stations, drifting buoys and other data sources available in near realtime. Additional in situ observations can be provided by ship of opportunity sailing in the Arctic. Calving of icebergs from marine terminating glaciers is a phenomenon which can cause accidents if vessels are close to the event. Observing such events over large areas is difficult because they are very localized and happens quickly. For selected glaciers, however, their motion can be monitored in realtime using laser or radar instruments, which has been demonstrated in a [SIOS project](#).

Figure 5.6. Calving of icebergs into the ocean. Photo by Martin Indreiten, UNIS.

Observing systems for earthquakes in the ocean are based on data from seismographic data from land stations. To obtain better data on earthquakes from the Arctic Ocean it is necessary to deploy Ocean Bottom Seismographs (OBS) in several locations. Observation of submarine volcanoes, hydrothermal activities and gas hydrates in areas such as in Mid-Atlantic Ridge will require special seafloor observatories, including use of advanced ROVs.

6. Requirements to observing platforms, instruments and methods

There are numerous methods to measure in situ physical and biological variables using both automated instruments and lab analysis of water samples. For many biological and biogeochemical variables analysis of water samples is necessary, because these variables cannot be retrieved automated in the same way as many physical measurements (e.g. temperature and salinity on moorings). This requires human effort and can be time consuming, implying that data cannot be delivered in near real time. To fulfil different user requirements for ocean data as defined by the list of Essential Ocean Variables (Table 1), the observing systems need to use a wide range of platforms, instruments and methods to collect observations from the whole water column. Section 6.1 describes methods for collecting biological, biochemistry and pollution data, which require human operations from ships and icebreakers. Section 6.2 describes the most common autonomous platforms and instruments

6.1 Methods for collecting biological, biochemistry and pollution data

Variable	Description
Phytoplankton	<p>Spatial and temporal variability in phytoplankton biomass and community composition can be estimated by measuring chlorophyll a concentrations (as an indication of the standing stock of phytoplankton). Direct measurements of Chl a concentrations require water samples from distinct depth that are filtered and analysed for Chl a concentration. These samples can also be used to determine community composition (biodiversity). Chl a biomass can also be estimated by remote sensing of ocean color. This is however limited to the sea surface, and the spatial coverage is highly limited in ice-covered waters. Using fluorescence sensors (fluorometers), Chl a concentrations can be measured in the water column. Vertical profiling with a fluorometer is common on ship-based campaigns, but fluorometers can also provide long-term data when attached to autonomous platforms (moorings, drifters, sea ice drift stations). Autonomous water samplers on fixed platforms (moorings) can take water samples at pre-programmed dates. Samples provide data on temporal changes in phytoplankton biomass and community composition.</p> <p>Sediment traps on fixed platforms sample sinking particles and provide data on temporal changes phytoplankton biomass and community composition.</p>
Sea ice communities: community composition & biomass	<p>Monitoring of ice algae biomass and diversity as well as community composition of sea ice micro-and meiofauna requires in situ sampling (sea ice coring or diving).</p> <p>Autonomous sampling techniques are limited with regard to sea ice flora and fauna. Camera systems or use of ROVs under the sea ice can provide insights into spatial variability of algae coverage and some estimates of macrofauna biomass and species composition.</p>

<p>Zooplankton: community composition & biomass:</p>	<p>In situ (ship-based) sampling of the zooplankton community requires net sampling. Samples provide data on community composition (biodiversity), population and size structure and biomass. Net opening area and mesh size determine which size class of zooplankton is sampled, ideally both mesozooplankton (100-2000µm) and macrozooplankton (>2000µ) should be sampled to get a more holistic picture of the community.</p> <p>Sediment traps on fixed platforms sample sinking particles, including zooplankton (either dead or those that actively swim into the traps) and provide data on temporal changes zooplankton community and biomass at the sampling site.</p> <p>An Underwater Video Profiler (UVP) can be deployed on fixed platforms (mooring) or autonomous platforms (e.g. floats, gliders). UVPs take images of zooplankton, and provide data on community composition, size structure and abundance over time or space. Data can be converted to biomass.</p> <p>Active acoustic sensors (echosounders) with high frequency transducers (>200 khz) on fixed (moorings) or mobile platforms (research vessels or autonomous platforms) provide data on zooplankton biomass and vertical distribution. Multifrequency sensors can also provide insight into biomass and distribution of different size classes.</p>
<p>Fish: community and biomass</p>	<p>Assessment of fish community composition requires trawling (ship based) which can be challenging in ice covered waters. Norway’s research icebreaker RV Kronprins Haakon has specialized equipment for trawling in ice-covered waters, and over the last few years there has been a modest but gradual build-up of trawl-based data on the fish community in the deep Arctic Ocean north of the Barents Sea.</p> <p>Active acoustics on ships of fixed platforms can provide data on fish biomass and distribution. Multifrequency sensors can also provide insight into biomass and distribution of different size classes.</p>
<p>Marine mammals</p>	<p>In situ aerial or ship based surveys provide data on species composition, abundance and distribution.</p> <p>Passive acoustics sensors on fixed or moving platforms provide data on species presence/absence. These sensors also monitor trends and changes in ocean sound, an EOVS adopted for the GOOS Biology and Ecosystems Panel.</p>
<p>Biodiversity in general:</p>	<p>eDNA-analysis provides information on presence/absence of species in a given water sample. This covers everything from microorganisms to marine mammals. Water samples can be taken in situ from ships or using autonomous water samplers.</p>

Biochemistry

<p>Nutrients:</p>	<p>In situ sampling of nutrients (nitrate, phosphate, etc.) requires water samples, usually taken from different depths to determine nutrient concentration through the water column.</p> <p>Nitrate and phosphate sensors can be deployed on moving or fixed platforms to provide data on spatial or temporal variability in nutrient concentrations.</p>
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<p>Ocean acidification</p>	<p>Measurements of total alkalinity, dissolved inorganic carbon and pH provide insights into the state of acidification. These can be measured in situ by taking water samples. Furthermore, sensors are available to measure pCO₂ and pH concentrations on fixed and moving autonomous platforms.</p> <p>pCO₂ and pH concentrations: sensors are available</p>
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Figure 6.1 Photos of common methods for marine sampling in the Arctic: (a) CTD and Rosette sampler with Niskin bottles, (b) Recovery of a moored Acoustic Zooplankton and Fish Profiler, (c) Multiple plankton sampler to sample the zooplankton community, (d) Sea ice coring, (e) Surface buoy of an ice-tethered observatory, (f) Recovery of a sediment trap. (Credit: a-d, f: Malin Daase; e. Kunuk Lennert).

Pollutants

<p>Microplastics:</p>	<p>Microplastics pollution is an emerging risk to marine organisms throughout all trophic levels as it can be of similar size to micro-organisms and thus digestible to a wide range of species and transferable through the food web. Microplastic are a global problem, including the Arctic, with the Barents Sea being one of the regions with highest microplastic concentrations. Measuring microplastic concentrations requires large volumes of water, as well as clean sampling procedures to avoid contamination. Standardized and universally agreed protocols for sampling and analysis, which are</p>
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	<p>required to enable intercomparison of data from different sampling campaigns, are still under development.</p> <p>Environmental pollutants, such as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) reach the Arctic mainly via long-range transport through atmospheric and ocean/river currents. Meanwhile, chemicals of emerging Arctic concern are commonly introduced as local contaminants from industries and infrastructure-related releases. Environmental pollutants have a negative impact on marine organisms and humans living in the Arctic as many of them bioaccumulate through the food web (see https://www.amap.no).</p> <p>Measuring contamination levels in water, sediment and organism is complex and requires requires in situ sampling (e.g. tissue samples of organisms).</p>
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Requirements to coherent observing protocols

In addition to standard observing instruments and analysis methods, there is a need to develop consistent protocols for sampling, analysis and archiving to assure comparability and data accessibility between field campaigns in different parts of the Arctic. The Atlantic-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatory (A-DBO) initiative works in that direction. A-DBO is part of a pan-Arctic network comprising a total of four regional DBOs, which started in the Pacific sector of the Arctic with a [dedicated website](#).

6.2 Autonomous platforms and instruments

Autonomous observing sensors and instruments are most advanced for physical variables, but there are ongoing efforts to develop autonomous sensors for biogeochemical and biological variables. In this section the most common autonomous observing platforms are described. They include moorings, gliders, Argo floats, buoys and unmanned surface vehicles.

Moorings (with subsurface floatation)	<p>A mooring is a collection of sensors and sampling devices connected to a wire and anchored on the seafloor (Fig. 6.2b). It is typically used to monitor ocean hydrography and currents, but other devices such as sea ice and biological sensors can be attached. A mooring is powered by batteries and can stay in the water for periods of 1–2 years, depending on the amount of power. Moorings can host a number of sensors for environmental data collection, providing high temporal resolution at the sampling site, including winter and polar night. For some power-hungry instruments like acoustic and optical sensors, battery capacity limits the amount of data that can be recorded.</p>
Gliders	<p>An ocean glider is an autonomous, unmanned underwater vehicle used for collecting profiling data along tracks steered by a pilot. Gliders can be equipped with a wide variety of sensors to monitor temperature, salinity, currents, and other variables. Data are transmitted when the glider is at the surface (Fig. 6.2a). The Norwegian National Facility for Ocean Gliders, NorGliders (http://norgliders.gfi.uib.no) is based at the University of Bergen's Geophysical Institute. The facility coordinates the operation of a fleet of ocean gliders operating in the Norwegian, Iceland, and Greenland Seas.</p>

Figure 6.2.(a) Illustration of the glider operation (provided by [WHOI](#)). (b) Mooring with example of instruments and subsurface floatation for deployment in ice-covered seas. Figure provided by UiT.

Figure 6.3. Left: the operational scheme of the Argo floats with example of temperature and salinity profiles. Right: deployment of an Argo float from a ship. Photo: H. Søiland, IMR.

<p>Argo floats</p>	<p>ARGO floats are profiling floats providing vertical profiles of pressure, temperature, salinity, and additional BGC parameters, as well as drift velocity of the floats (Fig. 6.3). At the surface, float position is determined by Global Positioning System (GPS) and the observed data are transmitted via an Iridium satellite communication system to a shore-based server (minutes of duration). The float then returns to its parking depth. The Norwegian Argo Infrastructure (NorArgo) deliver data from ca. 40 floats in the Norwegian-Greenland-Barents Sea.</p>
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Figure 6.4. Examples of ocean surface buoys with subsurface floatation and instruments. (a) Figure from NOAA (Baily et al., 2019), (b) Figure from Chen et al. 2023, (c). Figure from [WHOI Ocean Learning Hub](#).

<p>Surface buoys and vehicles</p>	<p>Open ocean surface buoys can be stationary with cable to the bottom or be freely drifting.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Surface buoy can have instruments hanging below with a cable connecting it to an anchor at the bottom. Surface buoys can have different configurations and subsurface instrumentation, as shown in Fig. 6.4 (2) Surface buoys can have drogues, also known as drifters, so they will follow the currents, providing Lagrangian measurement of the current (Fig.6.5). (3) Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USV) driven by wind, waves or propellers have developed into valuable autonomous platforms for oceanographic, meteorological and environmental data collection. Especially sail buoys are now quite advanced with capability to operate for months and cover large areas (Fig. 6.6)
<p>Sea ice platforms</p>	<p>Sea-ice drifting platforms have successfully been equipped with physical and environmental sensors, providing high spatial and temporal coverage. The simplest ice buoys only measure air pressure and temperature along with positions, which are transmitted in near realtime to the meteorological observing network. More advanced systems are the ice mass balance buoys measuring heat fluxed from ocean to atmosphere (Fig. 6.7a,b). For ocean measurements, ice-tethered platforms are used. They consist of a</p>

surface buoy and a vertical string of instruments at different depths or a profiling instrument for measurement collecting data in the upper 800 meter (Fig. 6.7c).

Figure 6.5. Example of drifters with different types of drogues (<https://nautiluslive.org/resource/ocean-drifters-teaching-animation>)

Figure 6.6. Example of sail-driven USV: The Saildrone during the 2022 Atlantic Hurricane mission with cameras and navigational instruments (<https://www.saildrone.com/news/7-saildrones-sailing-eye-hurricane>)

Figure 6.7 (a) Photo of a Seasonal Ice Mass Balance (SIMB) buoy deployed in the Arctic. Credit: Ryleigh Moore. (b) Data from a SIMB showing the season cycle of snow and ice thickness from October 2019 to July 2020 (Perovich, 2022). (c) Ice-tethered profiler from [WHOI](http://www.whoi.edu).

Seafloor observatories

There are several infrastructures in the North Atlantic serving as permanent seafloor observatories. These observatories can be a network of moorings, repeated glider transects, and repeated sampling sites. Examples of observatories are the [Hausgarten system](#) in the Fram Strait operated by Alfred Wegener Institute, and the [LoVe Ocean cable](#) in Lofoten-Vesterålen, which provide real-time physical, biological, and chemical observations. IMR is manager of the LoVe infrastructure (Fig. 6.8).

Figure 6.8 (a) Map of Hausgarten installations in the Fram Strait; (b) Cable transect and location of the scientific nodes from LoVe Ocean. From the LoVe Ocean website (<https://loveocean.no/>)

Robotic platforms for under-ice observation

Remotely operated vehicles (ROV) and Autonomous underwater vehicles (AUV) are developing rapidly and can contribute to ocean observations they carry a suite of different sensors and access areas which are difficult using traditional methods. ROVs with oceanographic, biological, biogeochemical, optical and acoustical sensors as well as video cameras can provide realtime data transmitted to the host vessel while they are steered by an operator to the required locations. A number of successful experiments to collect under ice data with ROV were demonstrated during the MOSAiC expedition (Anhaus et al., 2025). AUVs are also important because they can operate independently without direct human control and carry out different tasks, especially monitoring and data collection to support a wide range of applications, from surveillance to scientific research and commercial activities ([The Tech Vortex, 2025](#)).

Ship of opportunity systems

FerryBox is an operational method to continuously measure physical, chemical and biological parameters on board of ships-of-opportunity. FerryBox is a through-flow system installed on board of a ship-of-opportunity (ferry, cargo ship or research vessel) to measure automatically, continuously and unattended a series of important marine parameters. The sensors installed offer the opportunity to measure physical (salinity, temperature, turbidity), chemical (nutrients, pH, CO₂, DOC humic compounds, oxygen) and biological (chlorophyll, phytoplankton composition, dominant/harmful species) parameters. ([From EUROGOOS website](#)). Ferryboxes require fully autonomous systems which can operate unattended over long time. This is challenging because sensors and instruments need human interaction for calibration, check and maintenance prior and after deployment. In Norway Ferrybox systems are operated along the coast of Norway, between Tromsø and Svalbard and other areas (Fig. 6.9).

Figure 6.9 (a) Sailing routes where Ferrybox data are collected regularly; (b) MS Norbjørn has a Ferrybox system collecting data when it transports cargo from Tromsø to Svalbard

6.3 SMART cables

The *Science Monitoring And Reliable Telecommunications* (SMART) Subsea Cables initiative seeks to revolutionize deep ocean observing by equipping transoceanic telecommunications cables with sensors to provide novel and persistent insights into the state of the ocean (Rowe et al., 2022). Such cables are acknowledged by GOOS as an emerging network which can contribute to fill different gaps in the Global Ocean Observing System. The sensors will piggyback on the power and communications present in the cables and will collect data on three critical environmental elements of the deep ocean:

Temperature: SMART will characterize the changing climate with improved estimates of ocean heat content and sea level rise as relates to water's thermal expansion

Ocean bottom pressure: SMART will enhance ocean circulation modeling insofar as water flows from areas of high to low pressure, track sea level rise as relates to melting land ice, and improve tsunami early warning via direct measurement of overpassing waves;

Seismic acceleration: SMART will persistently monitor seabed seismic activity to improve early warning for earthquakes, tsunamis, and volcanoes, and yield superior risk assessments for vulnerable coastal areas.

To be useful for a wider range of ocean scientists, it is necessary to observe more than the three variables described above. The SMART system needs to be connected to, and transfer data from, moorings and other observing platforms in the water column and at the seafloor. There are more than one million kilometers of [subsea cables worldwide](#), which are repaired, replaced, or expanded on 10-20 year cycles. If some of the new cables could use the SMART concept, it would be of great value for the ocean science community.

The Vision 2030 report presents a vision and the results of a viability study for creating a resilient submarine cable system from Europe across the high Arctic Region towards East Asia, with possible landfalls in North America (NORDUnet, 2024). The report was created by [NORDUnet](#) and the Nordic NRENs (National Research and Education Network) in the context of the [Northern EU Gateways Project](#), co-funded by the European Commission (Fig. 6.10).

There are two planned subsea cable projects that may include SMART cable technology, the Pan Arctic Cable Solution (PACS) and Far North Digital (FND) cable systems. Both cable systems are planning to land on the coast of Northern Norway, but the exact landing locations are still to be

Figure 6.10 Cover page of the Vision 2030 document produced by [NORDUnet \(2024\)](#).

determined. The PACS and FND projects are actively exploring SMART cable solutions as a part of their final cable design. The SMART sensors would be integrated within the repeaters in the cable system and would need typically 70-90 km distance between each sensor and repeater (amplifier).

Data governance and delivery for SMART cables need to be more sophisticated for several reasons, following the principle “As open as possible — as closed as necessary.” Data management solutions need to address each repeater-sensor-location (Fig. 6.11) regarding ownerships, access and data storage. The current drivers for implementation of data management and governance policies for SMART cables are:

- Transmission chain ownership does not imply data ownership.
- Data ownership can change along the transmission chain.
- Each data owner can have a different general data access policy.
- Each sensor can have a different access policy depending on its location.
- Each sensor type might end up in a different (specialized) data repository.

The importance of ownership, policy and data center/repository changes for a SMART cable system, which traverses from EEZ-A through international waters to EEZ-B, is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Examples of ownership, data policy and data storage for three variables transmitted through a cable

Repeater #	Temperature Sensor			Pressure Sensor			Accelerometer		
	Data Owner	Policy	Data Centre	Data Owner	Policy	Data Centre	Data Owner	Policy	Data Centre
1 (in EEZ-A)	A	CC-BY	DC-1	A	CC-BY	DC-1	A	Possibly Diverted	ShakeAlert
10 (intern. Waters)	A, B, C	CC-BY	DC-X	A, B, C	CC-BY	NOAA	A, B, C	CC-BY	IRIS
20 (in EEZ-B)	B	Restricted	DC-2	B	Restricted	DC-2	B	Restricted	IRIS

Data Management issues will also need to consider

- Data volumes would be excessive.
- Vendor-independent data formats are not yet established.
- National security concerns would be an issue for all countries traversed.
- These concerns can be addressed in the same way shown in Table 2

A fiber cable itself can be used as a sensor for sensing acoustic, temperature and strain signals is becoming widespread both for terrestrial and subsea cable systems. Distributed acoustic/temperature/strain sensing (DAS/DTS/DSS) means that a laser source is injected into a fibre optic cable and the returned reflections are then interrogated and recorded (Fig. 6.12). The technique makes use of different scattering effects found in electromagnetic spectral physics where reflections occur each time a light source hits a medium which contains particles that are smaller than the wavelength of the laser source (e.g. Potter et al., 2024). Using classification algorithms based on machine learning/artificial intelligence, the fiber cable can be used detect, identify, and locate events such as pipeline leaks, power cable faults, and intrusion activities.

Some key features for a DAS enabled system:

- The DAS is based on rapid analysis of the backscatter of laser light along a fiber optic cable
- For now, DAS is limited to 100 km fiber length, but methods to address many 100-km sections simultaneously are developing rapidly (by e.g., [Alcatel Submarine Network](#))
- DAS would allow for continuous, real-time vessel, marine mammal detections.
- DAS offers very high precision of spatial resolution (< 1m over 10,000km)

In the EU [SUBMERSE](#) project, the DAS technology is tested on several subsea cables, one case is the cable between Longyearbyen and Ny-Ålesund, where ships, earthquakes and whales have been detected with DAS (Bouffaut et al., 2022). The method is as follows (Fig. 6.12): **(A)** On shore, an interrogator is connected to one end of an existing fiber optic cable to repurpose it into DAS. **(B)** It interrogates the fiber by sending laser pulses that are backscattered by anomalies while simultaneously, these defects are shifted under the effect of incoming acoustic waves, **(C)** The interrogator calculates time delays of the backscattered response at regularly spaced intervals along the fiber, named channels. Time delays are averaged over the gauge length and converted into longitudinal strain waveforms analogous to acoustic pressure. **(D)** DAS two-dimensional data is streamed in near-real-time to a remote data processing center.

Figure 6.12 Distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) for baleen whale monitoring (Bouffaut et al., 2022)

7. Data delivery chain

7.1 DATA OWNERSHIP

The collection and distribution of data from platforms (ship-based, fixed moorings and moving platforms) should be subject to national Norwegian regulations including “Forskrift om utenlandsk vitenskapelig havforskning i Norges indre farvann, sjøterritorium, økonomiske sone og på kontinentalsokkelen” ([FOR-2001-03-30-360](#)), and “Forskrift om opptak og annen bruk av informasjon om bestemt angitte bunnforhold” ([FOR-2023-12-15-2061](#)).

To ensure that the organization responsible for collecting and processing the data is recognized as the data owner, all data should be made available with a persistent identifier such as a DOI (<https://www.doi.org/>) and a licence to describe the rights of the owner and user of the data. Examples are Creative Commons licenses (<https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/licenses/>) and “[Norsk lisens for offentlige data](#)”.

7.2 DATA DELIVERY

NEAR REALTIME DATA

Access to near real time data is essential for marine forecasting services. In the Arctic Ocean, access to near real time data is a challenge. Data from vessels and other platforms with connection to the surface such as Argo floats and ocean gliders can be transferred to land stations using satellites. Traditionally, only low volume data has been transferred over satellite communication. This includes data from CTD, ferryboxes and weather stations. High volume data from vessels such as data from echosounders, hydrophones or video is delivered on physical media after the survey has finished.

Recent development in satellite coverage, i.e. introduction of [Starlink](#) and the [Arctic Satellite Broadband Mission](#) (ASBM) from Space Norway, gives the data collectors broadband capabilities for transferring data from platforms operating in the Arctic Ocean to land stations. The ASBM satellites are also addressing the challenges with unstable coverage in the arctic region ensuring broadband access in the Arctic from 65 degrees north to the North Pole.

Figure 7.1 shows the data delivery from a research vessel. Data is transmitted from the vessel to a [marine data assembly center](#) converted to standardized Copernicus format and uploaded to [Copernicus Marine Data Store](#). Data is normally available within a few hours after collection. A dedicated data assembly center is responsible for the data delivery to Copernicus. The data can be sent directly from the data collecting platform, or through the institution responsible for the data collection.

DELAYED MODE DATA

Delayed mode data include high volume data collected by research vessels not suitable for satellite transmission and data from subsurface moorings without data transmission capabilities. These data are transferred to land on physical media. The institution responsible for collecting the data is also responsible for publishing the data on a national and/or international data center as soon as possible after retrieval of the data.

Figure 7.1. NRT data delivery to Copernicus Marine Data Store

7.3 DATA ACCESS

Variable-specific data management centres do already exist, among others for seismic and oceanographic data. Requirements for secure data access would be:

- Well-defined data posting methods using standard data formats.
- Well-known data access methods, including APIs and the choice of many output data formats.
- Data repositories should adhere to the [FAIR principles](#)
- Data repositories should be [Core Trust Seal – certified](#)

User licence on the data with as few restrictions as possible, preferably a license compatible with [CC BY 4.0](#) The main Norwegian data repositories with oceanographic and Arctic data are:

- [Norwegian Marine Data Centre](#) (NMDC) hosted at Institute of Marine Research
- [Norwegian Polar Data Centre](#) hosted at Norwegian Polar Institute
- [Arctic Data Centre](#) at Norwegian Meteorological Institute
- [Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System](#) (SIOS)

The major European data centers for marine data are:

- [Copernicus Marine Data Store](#)
- [EMODnet](#): European Marine Observation and Data Network
- [SeaDataNet](#): Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management

Other examples of established repositories are [EPOS Data Portal](#) and [Earthscope/IRIS](#) for seismic data, NOAA [tsunami warning centre](#) for pressure data, [and Oceans 3.0 for oceanographic and acoustic data](#)

8. Concluding remarks

The Arctic Ocean environment is under pressure because of increased activities from many countries, rapid climate change with decreasing sea ice threats to the marine ecosystem. This involves loss of biodiversity, pollution, rising temperatures and acidification of the ocean, which is challenging both for ocean management and ocean industries (Blue Ocean – Green Future, 2021). To promote healthy and productive oceans it is urgent to build up holistic knowledge about the different ocean regions, especially in the high north where Norway has responsibility. This requires observing systems to deliver high-quality data for environmental monitoring, resource management, operational support and protection of infrastructures from the coastal zones to the deep oceans and into the ice-covered Arctic Ocean.

Climate research, environmental monitoring and marine services are the important drivers for further development and implementation of observing systems in Norwegian ocean areas including the Arctic. In this report the needs of in situ observing systems for different users and stakeholders have been discussed. There are many actors involved in the ocean observation value chain, from researchers collecting and analyzing data to target groups who need ocean knowledge for management and decision making (Fig. 8.1). The value chain starts with the observing technologies which are available for the different science disciplines, industrial activities and public services. The report elaborated on why ocean observations are needed by institutions involved in climate research, climate services, marine forecasting, marine ecosystems, environmental monitoring.

Figure 8.1 The Ocean Information Value Chain with ocean observations as the main pillar. (European Marine Board, 2021 and Virapongse et al., 2020).

Ocean observations follow international standards to serve climate research, marine services and protection of the environment. A number of intergovernmental agencies, international organisations, panels and committees play an active role to promote and coordinate ocean observation on global scale as well as in regions such as the Arctic Ocean.

The report has moreover elaborated on the requirements for observing platforms, instruments, methods for collecting, transmitting and managing the data. All types of observing systems depend on the available technologies, which need to be further developed. Improvement of sensors, more robust platforms, better data transmission and more advanced digital systems for management of data are needed to expand the Global Ocean Observing System, which is [Challenge 7 of the Ocean Decade](#) (Miloslavich et al., 2024). For underwater observing systems power supply and possibilities to recharge batteries limiting the observing capacity of the instruments. Data transmission from underwater platforms to the surface and further to shore via satellite is a bottleneck is also a challenge, but ROVs and AUVs can be used for this purpose.

Ocean observation under sea ice conditions is a challenge, but there is ongoing development to build robust platforms that can collect data over long time. Efforts are in progress to develop Argo floats to collect data in the Arctic Ocean. ROVs and AUVs equipped with different sensors are very promising for obtaining detailed observations below the ice where other observing systems are difficult to use. The ROV/AUV technology is used to perform very complex operations in offshore industry, and this technology has great potential to collect multidisciplinary data for marine research. Airborne drones can be used collect data from subsurface platforms when they ascent to the surface. With broadband communication, which is now established in the Arctic, the drones can operate in a large area with real-time data transmission to ships or to land.

The report has described how ocean observing can benefit from commercial submarine cables to transmit data in real time and collect data using the concept of SMART – Scientific Monitoring And Reliable Telecommunications. Since a transarctic communication cable is under planning (NORDUnet, 2024), it will be greatly beneficial to connect it to subsea observing nodes with acoustic transceivers, cameras, lights and other ocean observing instruments. The nodes should also have docking stations for AUVs so they can navigate between the node and other observing platforms to harvest data. A vision for an integrated observing system is to have a network of autonomous moorings with multidisciplinary sensors observing the full water column as developed in the High Arctic Observation System project funded by EU (hiaaos.eu; Sagen et al. 2025). The HiAOOS network should be sustained and connected to subsea cables which can transfer data from remote nodes to land. The network will provide an acoustic positioning system which will enable navigation and positioning of AUVs, Argo floats and gliders while they move underwater in the central Arctic.

This report, deliverable D4, is a contribution to the goal of the AOOS project, which is to develop a plan for implementation of an Arctic Ocean Observing System which will serve different scientific disciplines, public services and facilitate for innovation. The next reports in the project will address funding avenues for the observing systems (D3), specification and cost estimation of the observing

system components (D5), and data management, distribution and cost for the various types of data that will be part of the observing system.

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